

STUDY OF AN EXPERIMENTAL ION-EXCHANGE PLANT FOR PURIFYING ARTESIAN WATER

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Abstract. *The article is devoted to the current problem of softening hard water, typical for artesian springs. The authors propose a solution to this problem using a new ion-exchange unit developed in Uzbekistan. The purpose of the tests is to evaluate the efficiency of reducing water hardness caused by high calcium and magnesium ions after treatment on experimental ion-exchange equipment. The tests were carried out in the production conditions of the “Plom furnitur lux” company. The proposed approach provides an opportunity to better understand the processes occurring in the unit, as well as optimize operating parameters to achieve the best results in reducing water hardness.*

Keywords: *ion exchange unit, artesian water, water hardness, cationites, water softening, sorption.*

Introduction. Water resources are of priority importance in the industry of Uzbekistan, ensuring the functioning of various sectors. In the context of limited fresh water and growing demand from the population and enterprises, effective water management becomes necessary to ensure sustainable development. Particularly important is the use of artesian waters, which provide stable quality and quantity of water, contributing to increased productivity and competitiveness of enterprises. In this context, the right water management strategy can significantly affect the economic growth and environmental sustainability of the country [1,2].

High concentrations of alkaline earth metals such as calcium and magnesium result in hard water, making it unsuitable for many industrial and domestic applications. Hard water can cause scale formation in boilers and pipelines, which reduces the efficiency of equipment and increases its maintenance costs. In addition, high levels of hardness salts in wastewater can negatively affect water body ecosystems, disrupting the balance and deteriorating water quality. The protection of water resources in the republic is a priority and requires compliance with established laws and regulations [3].

Based on the authors' research, it was concluded that the use of cationites is an effective solution for desalination and softening of water [4-6], this method is relevant, environmentally friendly and economically advantageous. It was also taken into account that the choice of ion exchange equipment plays a key role, which contributed to the modeling of ion exchange equipment with predetermined properties. In this regard, the authors propose a promising solution for softening hard water using the developed ion exchange unit.

Methodology. Ion-exchange equipment for softening artesian water is an effective purification method that reduces water hardness by removing calcium and magnesium ions and replacing them with sodium ions. This is especially important for improving the quality of water used for domestic and industrial purposes. Softened water prevents scale formation in pipelines and equipment, which increases the service life of equipment and reduces maintenance costs. Thus,

ion-exchange equipment for softening artesian water has significant potential for improving the quality of water resources and sustainable development of water supply in Uzbekistan.

The ion exchange unit presented by the authors is equipped with four filters, collectors for feeding the initial solution and removing the purified solution, as well as collectors for sampling. Shut-off valves are provided to regulate the solution flow, which control the solution feed into the columns and its exit from them. In addition, the unit includes tanks for regeneration and washing of sorbents, as well as shut-off valves that regulate the feed of regenerating and washing solutions.

Fig. 1. Scheme of ion exchange plant for softening artesian water

The experimental ion exchange unit has a plastic structure, which ensures high resistance to corrosion. This is especially important when working with aggressive chemical environments, since plastic materials are not subject to destruction under the influence of acids and alkalis. In addition, the unit can withstand a wide range of temperatures, usually from 0 °C to 60 °C, which makes it suitable for various operating conditions. It also operates effectively in the pH range from 2 to 12, which allows the unit to be used to purify solutions with different chemical properties.

As an experiment, artesian water was used, coming from a well at the enterprise OOO “Plom furnitur lux”, based on the production of building metal structures and products [7].

The purpose of the tests is to test new ion exchange equipment when purifying artesian water using industrial cationite KU-2-8 based on styrene and divinylbenzene in H- and Na-forms. The sorption properties of ion exchange resins differ, so cationites and anionites are selected individually depending on the composition of the solution being purified. For softening water from hardness salts Ca^{2+} and Mg^{2+} , it is recommended to use cationite KU-2-8.

Fig. 2. Scheme of artesian water purification on an ion exchange unit in H-form

Fig.3. Scheme of artesian water purification on ion exchange unit in Na-form

To conduct the experiments, four filters were used, two filters were filled with cationite in the H⁻ form and two filters in the Na⁺ form, this scheme allowed to treat water under comparative conditions.

Water purification was carried out under dynamic conditions, with the installation connected via pipelines to tanks filled with artesian water from a well. The solution feed rate was 1.5 l/min (productivity per hour is 90 dm³/h, per day 2160 dm³/day), which was regulated by low-power pumps. The height of the fluidized bed of ion exchangers in the filter was 160 mm. The drainage system of the unit operated in a counter-current mode, i.e. the solution was fed into the filter from top to bottom and discharged from the filter from bottom to top. The amount of water undergoing purification was 60 liters in H⁻ and 60 liters in Na⁺ form. The time it took the solution to pass through the unit was ≈40 minutes. The process of softening artesian water in H⁻ and Na⁺ forms occurred simultaneously. The initial hardness values varied from 9.0 to 12.0 mg-eq/l, indicating a significant content of hardness ions. The pH of the water was in the range of 8 - 9.6, and the water temperature was 12 °C.

During the experiment, samples of incoming artesian water and samples after the water passed through the filters were taken every 10 minutes, and the temperature and pH of the environment were also monitored. Thus, the results show the efficiency of purification at each stage of processing. The results are presented in interval values in Table 1.

The experimental procedure for determining hardness was carried out according to GOST 4151-72 [8]. The experimental procedure for determining the total water hardness was carried out by the complexometric titration method using Trilon B (EDTA) according to GOST 4151-72. [9].

The total water hardness was calculated using the formula: $\chi = \frac{v \cdot 0,05 \cdot K \cdot 1000}{V}$

where v is the volume of Trilon B (EDTA) solution used for titration in cm³; K is the correction factor for the normality of the Trilon B solution; V is the volume of the water sample in cm³.

It is important to note that the discrepancy between repeated determinations should not exceed 2% of the total result. This method ensures accurate and reliable determination of the total water hardness, taking into account the influence of interfering substances.

The cleaning efficiency was calculated using the formula: $E_{cl.} = \frac{C_{in} - C_{out}}{C_{in}} \cdot 100$

Table 1. Purification of artesian water using an ion exchange unit

Water hardness before testing, mg-eq/l	Environment, pH	Temperature, t, °C	Artesian water in the boiler room after testing, mg-eq/l	
			KU-2-8	
			H-form	Na-form
9.0 - 12,0	8 - 9.6	12	0.4 - 0.5	0.3 - 0.1

The data in the table show that the hardness values varied from 9.0 to 12.0 mg-eq/l, which indicates a significant content of hardness ions in the water. After passing the water through the filters, the hardness in the H-form decreased to 0.4-0.5 mg-eq/l, and in the Na⁺-form to 0.3-0.1 mg-eq/l. In percentage terms, the purification efficiency shows 94.5-95.8% in the H form and 96.7-99.2% in the Na⁺ form.

The pH of the water was in the range of 8 to 9.6, after treatment the pH dropped to 6-6.5. This indicates a slightly alkaline environment, which may be acceptable for some technological

processes, but it is important to control this parameter to prevent corrosion. The water temperature did not change after treatment.

Results and discussion. The obtained results confirm the high efficiency of ion exchange filters in reducing water hardness. The range of initial hardness values is due to natural fluctuations in the content of hardness ions in artesian water. This explains the presence of a range of values, rather than a fixed figure. Differences in the ranges of values before and after purification are explained by natural variations in the source water, the characteristics of the ion exchangers used, and the experimental conditions. These data emphasize the importance of monitoring the quality of the source water and the efficiency of the purification systems to achieve optimal results.

Fig.4. Efficiency of softening artesian water on an ion exchange unit

It is obvious that the ion exchange unit using the cationite KU-2-8, H-form or Na⁺-form provides a significant reduction in hardness and has demonstrated high efficiency in removing Ca⁺ and Mg⁺ ions from water, which significantly improves the quality of artesian water. It has also been determined that the optimal flow rate (1.5 l/min) provides sufficient time for ion exchange, which improves the quality of purification.

The test results show that the use of an ion exchange unit for artesian water purification is an effective solution for ensuring the required water quality in production processes. It is recommended to continue monitoring water parameters to maintain optimal equipment operating conditions under other conditions.

Ion exchange wastewater treatment has a number of significant advantages that make this technology effective and in demand in various industries. Here are some of the main advantages of ion exchange treatment on simulated equipment:

- High efficiency of pollutant removal: Ion exchange systems are able to effectively remove ions of heavy metals, radionuclides, and other specific pollutants, which allows achieving high quality standards for purified water.

- Versatility of application: Ion exchange technologies can be used in various industries, including chemical, metallurgical, textile and others, which makes them a universal solution for wastewater treatment.

- Reduction of toxicity: The ion exchange process can significantly reduce the level of toxic substances in wastewater, which helps improve the environment and reduce risks to human health.

- Compactness of equipment: Ion exchange units often have compact dimensions, which allows them to be installed in limited spaces and simplifies integration into existing treatment systems.

- Resource savings: Ion exchange systems can be more cost-effective in the long term, as they allow water to be reused and waste disposal costs to be minimized.

- Ease of operation: Modern ion exchange systems are often equipped with automated control systems, which simplifies the operation and monitoring process.

- Low maintenance costs: Unlike some other purification technologies, ion exchange systems require relatively low maintenance and reagent replacement costs.

- Flexibility in settings: Ion exchange equipment can be adapted to the specific requirements of the enterprise, which allows it to effectively solve the problems of wastewater treatment with different characteristics.

- Reduction in sediment formation: Less sediment is formed during the ion exchange process compared to other purification methods, which simplifies further waste disposal.

- Stimulation of sustainable development: The use of ion exchange technologies contributes to a more rational use of water resources and a reduction in the negative impact on the environment, which is in line with the principles of sustainable development.

These benefits make ion exchange wastewater treatment an attractive choice for many facilities looking to improve the efficiency of their treatment processes and reduce environmental risks.

Conclusion. The use of ion exchange technologies not only improves water quality, but also reduces operating costs. Reducing hardness leads to a decrease in the frequency of equipment maintenance and a decrease in the cost of its repair. The economic benefit from using ion exchange units can be significant, especially in industrial production conditions. Thus, the results of the tests conducted confirm the feasibility of introducing ion-exchange technologies into water supply systems of boiler shops. Further study and optimization of the operating parameters of the units will allow achieving maximum cleaning efficiency and minimizing operating costs.

This article highlights the importance of using modern technologies to improve water quality and increase the efficiency of production processes in boiler houses.

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